

Working Paper

A Vedic solution to the problem of evil

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Abstract

There is a different way of relating our personal experience of the universe to lived reality. Science and the modern world make a claim that there is only one reality to the external world and that is objective reality. The Vedas, on the other hand, propose multiple levels of reality. There are at least six types of reality and three types of problems humans face. This analysis from a multidimensional perspective helps us breakdown the problem of evil into multiple buckets. This classification helps us understand that evil is not unidimensional. Knowing this perspective helps us understand that evil is but a creation of the mind and a mental construct. Thus, by changing one's mental paradigm, everyone can find a solution to this eternal problem.

Keywords: Problem of evil, Evil, Vedas, Upanishads, Types of realities, Realities

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1. Introduction

This is how the modern world teaches us to look at the universe, There is one reality all of us inhabit. Whether plants, animals or microbes, we all live in one objective universe. This is illustrated below.

Figure 1: Modern understanding of reality

One objective reality everyone lives in

This approach leads to the second inescapable conclusion – all the problems of the world are similar to each other. Every problem is your problem. The problem facing other living forms – like plants and animals are also your problem. The problems facing earth and the universe is also your problem. The issue with such a way of looking at the world is that one personalizes each problem, and everyone is not equipped to solve every problem in the world. Hence, despondency and depression are common problems in society.

Figure 2: Modern understanding of problems

The problem of evil is the question why is there evil in the universe? I argue that the modern scientific and objective universe is completely flawed and that the wrong paradigm is the reason why we can never find an answer. A change in paradigm can reveal a novel solution to the problem. The solution being that evil is a mental construct. If you change your mindset through yoga, the problem can be resolved immediately to one's subjective satisfaction.

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2. Methods

The Vedas look at the problem of evil from a completely new perspective.

Figure 4: Vedic understanding of reality

This is how the levels are explained.

Level 1 reality (reality beyond mind and body):

Permanent self: The first and foremost reality is that of your own existence. There is something inside you which exists. This is a first-person experiential understanding of your own existence. It is easy to think that this existence belongs to the mind or body. The Vedas interpret a pure “mind and body only” existence as wrong.

Level 2 reality (reality of the mind and body):

Non-existent mind: The existence of the mind is the next step in the hierarchy. The mind has thoughts that are temporary and vary every moment. The things that interest us as a baby do not interest us as a child, that of a child do not interest a young adult, that of a young adult do not interest a middle-aged adult, and the interests of an old adult do not interest anyone

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else. There is no reality or existence to the mind at all. It is just transient with no reality to it. It is Avidya (ignorance) that makes us think that the mind is real.

Ever changing body: The existence of the body is another reality. Unfortunately, the body decays and changes with time. All the cells in our body get replaced every couple of days. It is mind-boggling as to what is common to a just born child, adult and an old person. The bodies are completely different from time to time, and even minute to minute, but somehow there is a bizarre feeling of unity we personally experience. Where does this oneness come from? Probably, from the level 1 reality. We strongly misidentify with this changing body all the time. Death is also part of the changing reality. However, for the sake of the discussion, let us assume that this existence is somewhat real, since we experience it firsthand. This is a second hander reality, but we can sense it. In an eternally changing body, the ego is uncomfortable accepting that the dead body is also another change in the endless changes we undergo.

Level 3 reality (perceived lived reality):

People in our perceived circle: From a first-person perspective, we see and perceive only a small circle of the world at any moment. The bodies in this perceived world seem like our body, act like our body and think like our mind. We hence assume an equivalency of those bodies and our body. We really have no idea what is inside the mind. The people we perceive, as Descartes famously put it, could be straw puppets. They could be a simulation or robots or dreams or and a million other things. To discover the truth, one has to step outside the first-person reality and look inside the mind of another person. This is impossible. What controls the mind of other people will be an answer we can never learn. Even the answers to these puzzles can be a simulation, dream etc. The answer is unknowable. From this perspective, even our immediate relatives fall into this category. Their existence and reality are assumed by extrapolation of our inner self but can never be 100% confirmed.

Level 4 reality (lived reality beyond perception):

People outside our perceived circle: We read about people like leaders of the world separated by us in space. We read about people and dictators of the past separated by us in time. We may have never seen these people separated in time from us and can never see people who are separated in time from our timeline. These people are of an even lower level of reality. We have never perceived them through our senses directly; they are just a figment of our mind. People we have interacted with and now separated by us in terms of location, move from the earlier category 3 to this category 4, meaning that they move from being an object of senses to being an object of the mind. Even if we perceive them through videos, photos and letters; this reality is an inferior reality. Compared to level 3, because the level 3 is direct reality and level 4 is perception of a reflection of level 3.

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Level 5 reality (perceived non-living objects):

Compared to living beings, we have no idea of what non-living beings are. All we know is that they are not like us humans and not like other living beings. They are objects of the senses. We have no idea what they are, so we have invented a category called non-living. We know what they are not, they are not living in the way we and our relative (in the tree of life) live. If they live in a dissimilar manner from us, we will never know.

Level 6 reality (non-perceived non-living objects):

These are non-living beings outside our senses of perception, separated by space or time. These do not even have the sensory reality of level 5, but are a figment of imagination of the mind. This is the reality which is the furthest from us.

In a similar way, the following represents the Vedic understanding of problems in the world. The categories of problems will be analysed in the next section.

Figure 4: Vedic understanding of problems

3. Methods

These are the categories of problems we regularly get upset about. The numbers are calculated as an experiential estimate.

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A) Category A: Problems about people who were do not know directly (in the world) - 70% of problems

B) Category B: Problems about people we know directly (friends and relatives) - 20%

C) Category C: Our own problems - 10%

The issue with Category A is that we confuse level 4 reality (to which Category A belongs) as a level 1 reality. In addition, these are the events which happen the furthest away from us, hence we have no control over this situation. It is a pure creation of the mind, so it is more difficult to overcome unlike a situation in your vicinity over which one has more control. Finally, the stakeholders involved may themselves have contributed to the situation in some way, which we do not know about. Our mind does not have perfect and complete information, making our judgement flawed.

The issue with Category B is that because of ignorance of the highest truths of life (Brahma Gyana or Buddha nature), we have a wrong understanding of the world. Our current understanding of the world is brutally flawed and will fall apart if we give it the slightest poke. Hence, providence sometimes shakes us out of our stupor by shaking up things a little. Once, we pursue the highest truths, the pain and suffering automatically comes down. We should remember that all Jivas are serving out their own Karmic cycles and one cannot interfere with their Karma. This life is but a temporary and transient stage, where Karmic cycles intersect in this lifetime. All living beings are created not by us, but by a creator who put us together for a brief period. Samsara never ends with this life, hence there is no need to worry. When one knows not what happens after death, why fear? We fear because we are not dispassionate, we embrace the western model of one life. In Samsara, we will continue to meet again infinite times in the future, if we do not escape from Samsara. The problem is not of death like the western theology, but of infinite lives. There is no pressure to get Moksha now, it can happen after infinite lifetimes. However, to the logical person now is better than later. The sting of death vanishes in Samsara,

With reference to category C, our own problems are the most difficult to countenance. However, it is because of multiple factors. We falsely identify too much with our body. The body always degrades. The trick is to find Moksha before it becomes too bad. The events of the world, whether it be sickness or accidents, have no intrinsic meaning whether good or bad. It is our mind that colours the interpretation. We can have complete control over the mind, if we follow Dharmic faiths faithfully. Yes, to prevent us from being lost in Samsara and wasting this life, sometimes a kick in the back can jolt you awake. There is only one activity to do in life - the pursuit of true knowledge. Every other activity will only leave you wounded, depleted, and exhausted. The earlier one recognizes this truth; one will spend all their time only on the highest truth of Dharma.

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4. Discussion

We ask two questions as part of the discussion:

1) Is this a fanciful interpretation?

The Vedic interpretation is neither fanciful nor illogical. This is a logical extrapolation of the way we relate to the world. Ask yourself if you perceive the world objectively or subjectively. The answer is subjectively. There is no person in the world who looks at the world objectively. Objectivity is a utter lie of perception that is force-fed by science to all logical people. On the other hand, the Vedas propose an subjective universe, which is experientially correct and logically consistent with Science without the fake postulate of objectivity. I have argued earlier that subjective reality is intuitive and objective reality is artificial.ⁱ

2) Why haven't others thought of such an explanation?

The Vedas thought of this idea at least 7000 years ago. The actual date can never be determined because Sanskrit was orally transmitted for a long time before it was recorded as a written language. Since the textual Vedas are the oldest books in the world, the oral Vedas is probably far older. Africans and Europeans also had ancestral populations who had a personal relationship with nature. All these populations have been completely wiped out by Abrahamic monolithic perspectives. Indian has survived a thousand years of colonization and still retained its Vedic culture. Hence, India is the only place where the oldest and truest philosophy reigns supreme.

5. Conclusion

By creating a false construct of equality and equal opportunity, society tries to run away from the deeply unequal systems it has created. Instead of taking responsibility for injustice, it just blames individuals for acting out of line. This is where Samsara is one of the finest worldviews that exist. It is a pity that more westerners do not know about it.

The Hindu and Buddhist perspectives of Karma and Samsara are realistic, practical and mirrors the inherent disadvantages in every society. This worldview does not run away from the lived experience of the seekers; it gives them valuable tools to take control of the future. Most importantly, it gives a strong reason for virtuous behaviour. Others end up painting a picture of capricious divinity and the useless nature of virtue. If anyone had any common sense, one knows that virtue is important. Our societies suffer from lack of virtue, not the abundance of it. The only way to bring these values back is by embracing the Dharmic faiths.

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Acknowledgements

These are thoughts that emerges when dealing with the concepts of Karma and Samsara. I owe the germination of these thoughts to a discussion by Swami Sarvapriyananda with a reference to Bernardo Kastrup and consciousness.

References

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